

The Impact of Training Method on Programming Learning Performance

Authors : Chechen Liao, Chin Yi Yang

Abstract : Although several factors that affect learning to program have been identified over the years, there continues to be no indication of any consensus in understanding why some students learn to program easily and quickly while others have difficulty. Seldom have researchers considered the problem of how to help the students enhance the programming learning outcome. The research had been conducted at a high school in Taiwan. Students participating in the study consist of 330 tenth grade students enrolled in the Basic Computer Concepts course with the same instructor. Two types of training methods- instruction-oriented and exploration-oriented were conducted. The result of this research shows that the instruction-oriented training method has better learning performance than exploration-oriented training method.

Keywords : learning performance, programming learning, TDD, training method

Conference Title : ICBSR 2014 : International Conference on Business and Systems Research

Conference Location : Zurich, Switzerland

Conference Dates : July 30-31, 2014